

Heat stress in classrooms of different types of school buildings

Recommendations for action for heat adaptation in classrooms

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Approach and Goals of the Investigations

Climate change is leading to higher temperatures and more frequent heat waves, which poses a particular risk for children under 12. School classes spend more than six hours a day in classrooms, and high indoor temperatures can harm their health, well-being, and ability to learn. Since students have little control over the temperature, they are especially vulnerable. On top of this, most school buildings were not designed for increasingly hot summers and tend to overheat anyway due to the large windows in classrooms. The joint project KlimaKonform II therefore investigated how severe the heat stress is in classrooms of different school building types in Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt, and Thuringia, and which heat adaptation measures are most effective. This study uses a combined approach to analyse heat stress and thermal comfort in seven schools. These include three schools from the Wilhelmine era (1870–1918) in Plauen, Dresden, and Gera, two prefabricated concrete ("Plattenbau") schools (1970–1990) in Zeitz and Dresden, one post-war school (1952) in Dresden, and one newly built school, also in Dresden.

By comparing these buildings, it is possible to identify which building types are most vulnerable to extreme heat. The analysis follows the process shown in the diagram below and consists of several steps:

- Step a: Selection of representative school buildings
- Step b: Continuous measurement of classroom and outdoor temperatures from June to the end of September 2024 in two classrooms per school.
- Step c: Students and teachers in two classrooms per school were asked about their experience of the indoor climate during summer. The survey captures how temperature affects their comfort and well-being.
- Step d: In addition, detailed 3D models of the examined classrooms were created for thermal building simulations. This allows the effectiveness of various adaptation measures to be tested and compared in simulations.

By linking these steps (a to d), it is ensured that both objectively measured and subjectively perceived aspects of thermal comfort are taken into account.

Findings from the investigations

On the following pages, recommendations for reducing summer heat stress at schools are given based on the extensive investigations of the seven school buildings by means of temperature measurements, surveys and building simulations.

More detailed findings can be found in the respective profiles of the seven school buildings.

Key findings on heat stress in schools

1. Classrooms are generally much more heat-stressed than residential buildings due to their high proportion of windows and the lack of ventilation at night. In 2024, the measured room temperatures of various classrooms were often above 30 °C and a maximum of 33 °C.
2. Classrooms with unshaded, older window fronts facing east to southeast show a particularly critical heat load from early morning onwards due to solar radiation. Room temperatures can rise to over 30 °C even before the end of lessons.
3. Classrooms in prefabricated schools are not necessarily more heat-stressed than more solidly built schools from the Gründerzeit period. In short heat waves of less than 3 days, the massive outer walls (high thermal storage mass) of Gründerzeit schools ensure that high temperatures are dampened. However, in the event of a prolonged heat wave lasting longer than 3 days, room temperatures like those in prefabricated buildings occur, unless it is possible to cool down at night.
4. The survey of the pupils shows that from around 28 °C, more than half of the people in the classroom feel uncomfortable or even very uncomfortable. This can be used as the first recommendation of an acceptable limit temperature for classrooms. However, more detailed findings from physiological studies are still lacking here.
5. Limiting classroom temperatures to 28 °C during heat waves could only be proven in the measurements in 2024 for the new building of the Ehrenfried-Walther-von-Tschirnhaus Gymnasium in Dresden.

Central factors influencing heat stress in classrooms are:

- + The window properties, especially the proportion of transmitted solar energy and orientation
- + The possibility of window ventilation at night to dissipate heat in the classroom
- + User behaviour about window ventilation and shading

Recommendations for reducing heat stress in schools

The effectiveness of adaptation measures to reduce heat stress in the classroom depends on many factors such as the orientation of the windows, thermal storage mass and room occupancy. Nevertheless, recommendations for particularly effective measures could be derived from the investigations. These are listed below, sorted by effectiveness, starting with the highest:

A) Structural-technical heat adaptation measures

i) Reduction of heat input from solar radiation

- Install external sun protection (e.g. external blinds, external blinds): This should also be pulled down after class (this usually requires automatic control with a wind monitor). This can reduce heat input from the sun by up to 90%. In winter, an internal glare shield should be used to reduce heating energy consumption due to the heat input of the sun in the classroom.
- Install solar control glazing (additional coating of the glazing): Heat input from the sun can be greatly reduced, but the entry of daylight is still guaranteed. Solar control glazing is less effective than external shading, is not controllable and increases the heating energy required in winter because less solar energy penetrates the classroom and more artificial lighting is required.
- Attach highly reflective internal sun protection (with reflective coating on the outward-facing side): This can reduce heat input from the sun by up to 40%, which is less effective than external sun protection but can still significantly reduce exposure.
- Install triple glazing: The heat input from the sun is lower than with double glazing due to the additional pane of triple glazing (transmittance of solar energy is about 50% for triple glazing, about 70% for double glazing). Compared to double glazing in winter, triple glazing offers the advantage of significantly reducing heat losses through the large windows and thus the heating energy required.
- Shading by large trees or other greenery in front of the classroom windows: The sunlight is reduced by the foliage. Due to the average tree height, however, the shading effect is usually only present for the first two floors and requires that the greenery remains vital in summer. Due to the shedding of leaves in winter, the desired heat input from the sun in the classroom is given currently.
- Insulation and high reflection of the roof: For classrooms directly under a warm roof, an insulation thickness of the roof greater than 20 cm and a reflective light roof surface can greatly reduce heat stress

Recommendations for reducing heat stress in schools

ii) Enable effective (night-time) window ventilation

- The **majority of the window surfaces should be openable** in order to cool the classroom through effective air exchange when the outside temperatures are below those of the classroom.
- **All windows should be opened one to two hours before the start of lessons**, as at this time the outside temperature is usually significantly lower than that in the classroom.
- **Install clearly visible thermometers** to visualize the current outside and room temperature and thus make it clear when it makes sense to ventilate the classroom due to cooler outside temperatures (like the CO₂ traffic light).
- **Install automatic, weather-controlled window control**, which tilts some of the classroom windows open at night or opens completely when it is cooler outside and neither rains nor storms. In this case, a consideration of burglary protection is relevant and may therefore only be possible for upper floors.

iii) Installation of a ventilation system with intelligent operational management

- **Automatic, sensor-controlled commissioning of the ventilation system** as soon as the outside temperature is significantly below the indoor temperature of the classrooms, i.e. mainly in the late night and early morning hours.
- **On hot days**, the ventilation system should be switched off **after the end of lessons** in order not to transport warmer outside air from the hot afternoon hours into the classrooms.
- In winter, a ventilation system offers the advantage that, when the heat recovery unit is installed, it significantly **reduces heating energy consumption** and ensures good air quality and reduced germ load in the air.

iv) Installation of ceiling fans

- In recent years, modern ceiling fans (without visible rotor blades) have been installed in numerous schools in Toulouse (France), which has **reduced the perceived temperature by up to 3 °C**.

Recommendations for reducing heat stress in schools

B) Behavioural heat adaptation measures

- **Sensitisation** of teachers and pupils to **heat-adapted window ventilation** at the beginning of summer, which means
 - Open windows when classroom temperature is above 25 °C and outside temperature is cooler (thermometers with indoor and outdoor temperatures are helpful for this)
 - Close windows when outside temperature exceeds classroom temperature (only open briefly for fresh air supply)
- **Cross ventilation** of the classroom via open classroom doors, if this does not negatively affect the lessons acoustically.
- Shutting down the external sunshade, if fitted.
- Draw **internal glare protection (curtains)** if there is no external sun protection to **avoid direct sunlight** on pupils
- Advice to pupils to drink enough to ensure the body's temperature regulation through perspiration.

C) Structural and school organisational heat adaptation measures

- **Holiday periods** should be in the summer months with the highest temperatures, i.e. **July and August**.
- **Uniform regulations on "shortened lessons"** in the event of severe heat stress in schools should be defined across the board and not left to each school itself.
- **The greenery on the school grounds** is to be maintained, and the existing greenery is to be expanded to reduce the temperatures in the outdoor space and to enable shading of classrooms.
- **Less heat-stressed classrooms should be used** (north-west sides, lower floors) if these capacities are available in the school.
- **Dealing with heat stress should be addressed in class** in order to learn how to deal better with heat in the private sphere.

Summary of recommendations

Effective heat adaptation in classrooms of existing school buildings is only possible if structural-technical heat adaptation, behavioural adaptation and structural and school organisational measures are considered and implemented together.

 Positive/negative effect